

Cadenas de búsqueda

A continuación, se relacionan las cadenas de búsquedas aplicadas en los diferentes bases de datos:

Base de datos	#	Cadena	Cadena de búsqueda ajustada	Configuración
IEEE	1	((("All Metadata":cyber-physical systems) AND ("All Metadata":CPS) AND ("All Metadata":cybersecurity evaluation model) AND ("All Metadata":ontology evaluation model) OR ("All Metadata":assessment model) AND ("All Metadata":quantum cybersecurity model) AND ("All Metadata":cybersecurity frameworks) AND ("All Metadata":identify improvement opportunities) OR ("All Metadata":cybersecurity enhancement) OR ("All Metadata":quantum risk assessment) AND ("All Metadata":quantum era) AND ("All Metadata":critical infrastructure))))	((("All Metadata":cyber-physical systems) AND ("All Metadata":CPS) AND ("All Metadata":cybersecurity evaluation model) AND ("All Metadata":ontology evaluation model) OR ("All Metadata":assessment model) AND ("All Metadata":quantum cybersecurity model) AND ("All Metadata":cybersecurity frameworks) AND ("All Metadata":identify improvement opportunities) OR ("All Metadata":cybersecurity enhancement) OR ("All Metadata":quantum risk assessment) AND ("All Metadata":quantum era) AND ("All Metadata":critical infrastructure))))	Filters Applied: Journals 2020 – 2026 / 31 Enero 2026
ACM	1	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS" AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "quantum cybersecurity model" OR "quantum risk assessment"))	[[All: "cyber-physical systems" OR [All: "cps"]]]AND [[All: "quantum era" OR [All: "quantum threats" OR [All: "quantum cybersecurity model" OR [All: "quantum risk assessment"]]]	AND [E-Publication Date: (01/01/2020 TO 01/31/2026)]
	2	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS" AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model"))	[[All: "cyber-physical systems" OR [All: "cps"]]]AND [[All: "cybersecurity evaluation model" OR [All: "ontology evaluation model" OR [All: "assessment model"]]]	AND [E-Publication Date: (01/01/2020 TO 01/31/2026)]
	3	((("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS")) AND (("cybersecurity in critical infrastructure" OR "critical infrastructure") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks"))	[[All: "cyber-physical systems" OR [All: "cps"]]]AND [[All: "cybersecurity in critical infrastructure" OR [All: "critical infrastructure"]]] AND [[All: "best practices" OR [All: "comparative analysis" OR [All: "cybersecurity frameworks"]]]	AND [E-Publication Date: (01/01/2020 TO 01/31/2026)]
	4	((("cyber-physical systems" AND "CPS")) AND ("cybersecurity in critical infrastructure" OR "critical infrastructure") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement"))	[All: "cyber-physical systems" AND [All: "cps"] AND [[All: "cybersecurity in critical infrastructure" OR [All: "critical infrastructure"]]] AND [[All: "identify improvement opportunities" OR [All: "cybersecurity enhancement"]]]	AND [E-Publication Date: (01/01/2020 TO 01/31/2026)]

		opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement"))		
ScienceDirect	1	("critical infrastructure" OR "cybersecurity in critical infrastructure") AND ("quantum cybersecurity model" OR "quantum risk assessment" OR "quantum threats" OR "quantum era")	("critical infrastructure" OR "cybersecurity in critical infrastructure") AND ("quantum cybersecurity model" OR "quantum risk assessment" OR "quantum threats" OR "quantum era")	Filters Applied: Journals 2020 – 2026
	2	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("cybersecurity enhancement")	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("cybersecurity enhancement")	Filters Applied: Journals 2020 – 2026
	3	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks")	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks")	Filters Applied: Journals 2020 – 2026

Cadenas aplicadas hasta el 31 de enero de 2026